

Effects of submergence timing and application of azospirillum and K on direct seeded rice

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Farmers who depend on the Cauvery system in Tamil Nadu have been forced to direct seed rice because of frequent delays in receipt of canal water. K has been reported to help plants recover from

moisture stress by maintaining higher leaf expansion rates, higher chlorophyll contents, and stomatal resistance. It also promotes yield stability and increases productivity under moisture stress by synthesizing more proline. Azospirillum increases root proliferation and provides facilities to get through drought conditions by remaining in the root interspace.

We conducted an experiment to find out if K and azospirillum can be used to enhance productivity under restricted water conditions and to what extent submergence can be delayed after seeding.

The soil is sandy loam (Typic Haplustalf), with neutral pH, low available N and K, and medium P. The experiment was laid out in a split-plot design during 1989-90 and 1990-91 monsoon seasons. ADT38 rice was the test variety. The main plot was submerged 30, 45, and 60 d after seeding (DAS) to simulate water receipt from the canal. Subplots were treated with K at different times with and without azospirillum inoculation. Nutrient levels were kept uniform at 150-26-50 kg NPK/ha. Rice received only rain until first submergence, after which it was kept wet.

Table 1. Effect of time of submergence (30, 45, 60 DAS) and application of azospirillum and K on grain yield of direct sown ADT38 rice. Tamil Nadu, India.^a

Treatment no.	Time of K application and azospirillum inoculation	Grain yield (t/ha)											
		1989-90				1990-91				Pooled data (mean of 2 yr)			
		30	45	60	Mean	30	45	60	Mean	30	45	60	Mean
1	100% K basal	5.2	4.8	4.5	4.8	4.6	4.8	4.2	4.6	4.9	4.8	4.4	4.1
2	1 + azospirillum	6.3	5.2	4.9	5.5	5.5	5.4	4.5	5.1	4.9	5.3	4.7	5.3
3	50% K basal + 25% at tillering + 25% at PI	4.9	5.2	4.7	4.9	5.0	4.8	3.8	4.6	4.9	5.0	4.2	4.7
4	3 + azospirillum	6.1	5.7	4.9	5.5	6.1	5.6	4.9	5.5	6.1	5.6	4.9	5.5
5	50% K basal + 50% at tillering	5.1	5.0	4.5	4.9	4.8	5.2	4.2	4.7	4.9	5.1	4.3	4.8
6	5 + azospirillum	5.6	5.5	4.9	5.3	5.6	5.6	5.1	5.5	5.6	5.6	5.0	5.4
7	50% K basal + 50% at PI	5.2	5.2	4.8	5.1	5.1	4.8	4.9	4.9	5.2	5.0	4.8	5.0
8	7 + azospirillum	5.9	6.0	5.3	5.7	5.7	5.5	5.4	5.5	5.8	5.7	5.4	5.6
	Mean	5.6	5.3	4.8	-	5.3	5.2	4.6	-	5.4	5.3	4.7	-
	Time of submergence	SE	LSD	SE	LSD	SE	LSD	SE	LSD	SE	LSD	SE	LSD
	Time of K application and azospirillum	0.1	0.4	0.2	0.5	0.1	0.3	0.1	0.3	0.1	0.3	0.1	0.3
	Interaction	0.3	ns	0.3	ns	0.2	ns	0.2	ns	0.2	ns	0.2	ns

^a ns = nonsignificant.

Table 2. Effect of time of submergence (30, 45, 60 DAS) and application of azospirillum and K on straw yield of direct sown ADT38 rice.

Treatment no.	Time of K application and azospirillum inoculation	Straw yield (t/ha)							
		1989-90				1990-91			
		30	45	60	Mean	30	45	60	Mean
1	100% K basal	5.61	5.23	5.02	5.29	5.59	5.16	4.70	5.15
2	1 + azospirillum	6.36	5.41	5.09	5.62	6.43	5.39	5.18	5.67
3	50% K basal + 25% at tillering + 25% at PI	5.49	5.44	5.04	5.32	5.31	5.51	4.86	5.73
4	3 + azospirillum	6.48	5.98	5.30	5.92	6.34	5.83	5.13	5.77
5	50% K basal + 50% at tillering	5.50	5.49	5.22	5.40	5.42	5.36	4.72	5.17
6	5 + azospirillum	5.98	5.73	5.12	5.61	5.99	5.62	5.03	5.55
7	50% K basal + 50% at PI	5.64	5.56	5.16	5.46	5.55	5.38	4.94	5.29
8	7 + azospirillum	6.32	6.17	5.74	6.08	6.29	6.18	5.63	6.03
	Mean	5.92	5.63	5.21	-	5.87	5.56	5.02	-
	Time of submergence	SE	LSD	SE	LSD	SE	LSD	SE	LSD
	Time of K application and azospirillum	0.11	0.37	0.14	0.47	0.11	0.37	0.13	0.37
	Interaction	0.19	ns	0.23	ns	0.23	ns	0.23	ns

Submergence at 30 or 45 DAS produced optimum grain yield; further delay in irrigation water reduced yield (Table 1). Azospirillum exhibits an augmentative effect. Applying a split of K—half seeding, half at panicle initiation (P1)—benefited rice more than when all K was applied as basal or in three splits.

Straw yield followed a similar trend (Table 2).

Farmers can obtain higher productivity in direct seeded rice that is later converted to wet rice by applying irrigation water at 45 DAS, azospirillum inoculation, and K splits basal and at PI. □

Planting rainfed winter crops in rice fallows under different N and tillage treatments

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We evaluated the productivity and production economics of five winter crops sown in rice fallows under rainfed conditions before and after the harvest of transplanted irrigated rice under two tillage conditions and two N levels. Soil is clayey loam with a pH of 6.8, 0.6% organic C, 0.06% total N, 20 kg available P/ha, and 170 kg available K/ha. The experiment had 7.5- × 2.0-m plots laid out in a split-split-plot design with four replications. Tillage was in the main plots, crops in subplots, and N in sub-subplots.

Establishment of rainfed winter crops under different N fertilizer and tillage treatments after wet rice, West Bengal, India, 1989-90.^a

Treatment	Seedlings (no./m ²)	Branches (no./plant)	Grains (no./panicle or pod)	1,000-seed wt(g)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Straw yield (t/ha)	Net return (\$/ha)
<i>Crops</i>							
Lentil	115	9.5	1.6	17.0	0.73	2.71	361
Grasspea	85	7.4	2.4	62.9	1.40	2.83	518
Mustard	303	3.2	2.8	2.1	0.33	1.04	284
Wheat	115	136.7	24.3	37.9	1.30	2.21	249
Beans	28	4.7	2.6	85.7	0.59	2.30	331
Mean	129	32.3	6.8	41.2	0.84	2.23	320
LSD (0.05)	22	5.2	6.7	9.8	0.95	1.04	
<i>N level (kg/ha)</i>							
0	131	27.6	5.7	38.6	0.73	2.00	281
50	127	31.0	7.8	43.9	0.95	2.46	360
Mean	129	32.3	6.8	41.2	0.84	2.23	320
LSD (0.05)	ns	5.1	1.2	5.1	0.07	0.31	
<i>Tillage number</i>							
0	128	33.8	7.6	40.8	0.88	0.63	382
4	130	30.8	5.9	41.6	0.79	1.82	259
Mean	129	32.3	6.8	41.2	0.84	2.23	320
LSD (0.05)	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	0.37	-

^a Basic IR36 rice yielded 4.1 t/ha with net return of US\$507/ha.

IR36 rice was transplanted 20 Jul 1989, 21 d after seeding, at 25- × 25-cm spacing with 4 seedlings/hill. We applied 60-30-30 kg NPK/ha at planting. The crop was harvested on 31 Oct.

Lentil (*Lens culinaris*, cv. L-9-12), grasspea (*Lathyrus sativas*, cv. Nirmal),

mustard (*Brassica campestris*, cv. RW351), wheat (*Triticum aestivum*, cv. UP262), and beans (*Phaseolus vulgaris*, cv. PDR14) were broadcast seeded over the rice crop 1 d before harvest under zero tillage (ZT) conditions. The same crops were also broadcast seeded on 30

Nov after conventional tillage (4 times) with bullocks (CT). Seeding rate in kilograms/hectare was 20 for lentil, 30 for grasspea, 6 for mustard, 100 for wheat, and 50 for beans. We broadcast no N or 50 kg N/ha as per treatment 1 d after harvest in ZT and at plowing in CT. With ZT, lentil was harvested on 3 Feb 1990, grasspea on 1 Feb, mustard on 27 Jan, wheat on 7 Feb, and beans on 2 Feb. With CT they were harvested on 15 Feb, 10 Feb, 27 Jan, 7 Feb, and 11 Feb, respectively.

Rainfed winter crops can be established in rice fallows, although yields differ significantly among crops. Grasspea (grain and stover) yielded more than the other crops (see table).

After transplanting irrigated rice, rainfed winter crops yielded more grain and stover under ZT than under CT (see table) because of higher soil moisture and longer growing period. Winter crop grain and straw yields responded significantly to 50 kg N/ha. Grasspea had the highest net return, followed by lentil and beans. N fertilization gave higher net returns than the control, as did ZT compared with CT (see table).

Integrated pest management—diseases

A trap plant method to predict the occurrence of rice blast (BI)

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B1 caused by *Pyricularia oryzae* Cav. is a serious rice production constraint. Rice straw and seeds and weeds are primary sources of infection.

Managing B1 requires a forecasting system in which weather conditions and aerial spore densities are monitored. We used trap plants in a ricefield to estimate the spore population during Jan 1990-Mar 1991 in Amphoe Seinoi, Noonthaburi Province. Rice variety RD23, which is highly susceptible to B1, was planted in five seedling boxes (5 × 10 cm). We placed 7-d-old RD23 seedlings in the field for 2-3 d and then brought them into a

greenhouse. Conspicuous leaf B1 lesions were counted on each plant about 5 d later. We stuck slides coated with gelatin to the lesions to estimate spore production.

On 31 Jan 1991, we observed 100 infected trap plants, each with an average of 5 lesions and a mean sporulation of 110 spores/lesion (see figure). We advised farmers to spray tricyclazole 75% wettable powder in the neighboring fields.

At the booting stage (19 Feb), 80 infected trap plants had a mean sporulation of 80 spores/lesion. We issued the same recommendation to farmers.

By the panicle growth stage (22 Feb), the lesions/plant, spores/lesion, and diseased trap plants were reduced (see figure). By applying the treatment, farmers obtained a high grain yield (6.7 t/ha) with a net return of about US\$950.

These results suggest that trap plants can be used to predict the occurrence of B1. Rice trap plants should be placed in

ricefields 2 wk before sowing and then at 30, 55, 65, and 75 d after sowing to monitor disease progress. □

Population of *P. oryzae* and leaf blast incidence at different rice growth stages. DI = disease incidence.

Surveys of disease or insect incidence/severity in one environment are useful only if the information is related to other variables (e.g., climatic factors, crop intensification, cultivars, management practices, etc.). By itself, information on incidence in one environment does not increase scientific knowledge.